

IMPORTANCE OF EDUCATION QUALITY MANAGEMENT

Fayzullaeva Madina Abdumumin kizi

1st year master's student in the field of "Management
of educational institutions"

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Annotation: In this article, the reform of the education system in Uzbekistan at a new stage of development, the creation of a high-quality structure of education, the transformation of continuous education into a new effective process, as well as the use of advanced world experience, the application of the methodology of improving the quality of education in developed countries achievement, the role and importance of the system are thoroughly analyzed.

Keywords: Quality management, legalization of additional education, nostrification, efficiency, international conventions.

Modern education requires strict control and fair management. Ensuring the harmony of control and management in education is the key to quality and efficiency. If the quality of education is not systematically controlled in the educational system of Uzbekistan, certain problems arise in the educational process. Therefore, educational management should take into account the educational process, the type of education, its capabilities, and thereby ensure the effective operation of quality management. The change in the effectiveness and quality of management in education is related to the correctly selected management model and the practice of its consistent application in the continuous education system. After all, "The success of reforms, our country's taking a worthy place among the developed and modern countries of the world is inextricably linked with the development of science and education, and our ability to compete in this regard on a global scale [1; 446]. It also shows the impact of education on social development.

At the new stage of Uzbekistan's development, the issues of reforming the education system, creating a quality education structure, and turning continuous education into a new effective process are becoming more and more urgent. These tasks require the development of a fair management and universal control system over education and the improvement of existing forms. Therefore, today there is a growing need for additional research and new approaches to improve the quality of continuous education, expand its capabilities, and improve the effectiveness of the control and management process. Ensuring the quality of education remains a priority in all countries of the world.

Quality management of an educational institution is a complex system that includes the process of organization, provision and management of education

and is mainly related to the educational process. According to our researchers who conducted research on the quality of education, "The goal of management in education is to increase the level of knowledge of students in general management theory, to form their ability to apply this knowledge in practice" [2.]. In other words, the main attention should be focused on increasing the knowledge of students and developing their ability to apply the knowledge they have acquired in practice.

It is important that the control and management system in education is organized in a professional, open, transparent and fair manner, with logical consistency. Therefore, how well the work is carried out in the educational institution, the correct choice of the management model, and the fair organization of educational quality control have a strong impact on educational efficiency. [5.4]. At the same time, external control mechanisms have been developed for the state education system, through which certification and monitoring of educational institutions is carried out. Procedures for learning, controlling and influencing management through certification are being improved every year and adjusted to international standards. Such work in educational institutions encourages internal control departments to work honestly and legally, teachers to work more carefully, to identify shortcomings and eliminate them.

According to another researcher, "it is necessary to manage all factors together using a systematic approach in solving the problems of educational quality. The loss of any factor from this chain leads to the violation of the educational quality management system. Based on the obtained data, the analysis of the quality of education and effective management requires the identification of a number of quality characteristics of education" [3, 19]. Consequently, the quality of education has a positive effect on increasing the effectiveness of its analysis and control, on the organization of management based on its results. Indeed, a systematic approach and accurate analysis are the basis for the development of management weaknesses and control mechanisms.

The State Inspection of Education Quality Control under the Cabinet of Ministers is the body that controls and coordinates the education system in Uzbekistan. Its activity is regulated by the decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On improving the activities of the State Inspectorate for Quality Control of Education under the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan". In addition, each educational institution is controlled and regulated by the Law on Education and other regulations, as well as by its governing board [1; 446].

In developed countries, the control of the quality of education is also entrusted to the state, and continuous education is consistently and systematically managed on the basis of standards set by the state at all stages and in the educational process.

It is important to create a bank of uniform requirements for the quality of education in the world, to ensure control over general requirements and thereby develop mechanisms for monitoring the quality of education. Significant work is being done by UNESCO to organize education on the basis of uniform requirements for the whole world, to implement control and management on the basis of uniform documents, to unify or recognize, legalize and nostrify documents issued for the completion of education. At the same time, international conventions were adopted. In general, the work in this regard has made significant progress, and the whole world supports this process.

The reforms carried out in Uzbekistan in recent years have created a significant legal basis for the modernization of the education system, the introduction of control and management procedures in accordance with international standards, and the creation of cooperation mechanisms in the field of continuing education. In particular, in 2017, the State Inspectorate for Quality Control of Education was established under the Cabinet of Ministers in order to control the quality of education and regulate the impartial assessment of the quality of personnel training [4]. At the same time, problems, centralized and bureaucratic obstacles remain in the work of modernizing the control and management system, creating an effective educational environment that affects the quality of education through the established legal framework.

It is important to adjust the education of students to state standards by monitoring the quality of education, analyzing the criteria for the formation of basic competencies and the dynamics of the growth of skills in natural sciences. At the same time, it is important to identify and eliminate deficiencies in the field of education and uncoordinated aspects of cooperation, as well as the factors that cause them. However, this is not a solution to the problem, but a way to correct the situation. Therefore, in order to improve the quality of education, modernize continuous education, and solve its problems, it is necessary to change management principles, criteria and approaches, and to carry out control work. For example, tests, questionnaires, or other forms of test materials used in international assessment programs encourage students to think freely, reason logically, and analyze. Our tests are aimed at developing students' memory of the content and are developed within the framework of the current curriculum and

textbooks. The main reason for this is that we have not yet introduced the science of testology, and the issue of teaching the rules of test design has not been resolved.

Therefore, in Uzbekistan, the use of advanced foreign experience, the adoption of the methodology of developed countries to improve the quality of education, the liberalization of control over the quality of education, the abolition of centralized management, the elimination of bureaucratic obstacles, tasks in this regard Creating a simple and fair system is a priority. For example, foreign experience is being used to improve the quality and efficiency of education by updating the methods of evaluating and monitoring the development of science and education.

In conclusion, it can be said that today, based on the priority directions of the socio-economic development of our country, the fundamental improvement of the education system, the fundamental revision of the personnel training system, and the creation of educational opportunities at the level of international standards the necessary work is being done. Therefore, in order to ensure the quality of education and introduce it into the national education system, it is one of the urgent tasks to study the organizational and pedagogical features of improving the control and management structures of advanced foreign countries.

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